

**TRANSIT ROUTES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN WHICH
IMPACT ON ORGANIZATION AND TRAFFIC SAFETY**

Murodali Nurdinov Alijonovich¹

Furkatbek Dumakhonov Shuxrat o'g'li²

¹ associate professor, Department of Vehicle engineering, Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

² Senior Lecturer, Department of Vehicle engineering, Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7197165>

Location and development of the main networks of world transport.

There is a good reason to call automobile transport the transport of the 20th century. It was created at the beginning of our century and now the car has become an integral part of our life. The length of the roads is increasing, 24 mln. km. reached About half of it belongs to five countries - USA, India, Russia, Japan and China. Automobiliation has reached an all-time high in the United States. Here, on average, there are 600 cars per thousand people. In many countries of Western Europe, this indicator is somewhat higher: 300-400 and even more [1-2].

The most important process to keep in mind when transporting goods in international road transport is: Traffic safety [3].

Traffic safety includes the following components:

- traffic safety (TS);
- environmental safety;
- personal safety of moving vehicles and drivers of transported goods;
- organizing the work of drivers in compliance with traffic safety requirements;
- compliance of drivers with regulatory requirements in work mode;
- organization of medical examination of drivers before the flight (and after the flight);
- creating conditions for improving the skills of drivers and ATK specialists. After getting a driver's license, drivers must undergo training and practice every year. Even if there is a break in the practice of driving a car for more than a year, it also happens when switching from one direction (route) to another or from one type of transport to another [4-5];
- Analysis of accidents and violations of traffic rules (including motor vehicles); in this regard, study and take into account the accident;
- ensuring that the technical condition of moving vehicles meets the requirements of road safety;

In this regard, the government of our Republic, in order to create convenience for international carriers and to improve international relations:

- 44 routes intended for the transit of foreign motor carriers through the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 9, 2011 No. 323 [6-7].

With the increase in the volume of road transport, the Cabinet of Ministers in order to create additional favorable conditions for the transit movement of foreign motor carriers across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to increase the transport and transit potential of the republic, and to ensure the uninterrupted transportation of export-import goods by road transport By the decision No. 492 dated June 30, 2018, the number of these routes was set at 99.

International by cars through the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan transit routes for transportation

Table 1

s/n	Name	Length km	The name of the highways in the route
1	Route 1	268	A-381-A380-4P156-4P156g
2	Route 2	680	A-381-A380-M37
3	Route 3	1028	A381-A380-M39-4P23
4	Route 4	1035	A381-A380-M39-M39a
5	Route 5	1192	A381-A380-M39-M39a-M41
6	Route 6	1112	A381-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-4P20
7	Route 7	1330	A381-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
8	Route 8	1096	A381-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
9	Route 9	424	A381-A380
10	Route 10	480	4P156g-4P156- IY15km-A380-M37
11	Route 11	828	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M39-4P23n
12	Route 12	835	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M39-M39a
13	Route 13	992	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M39-M39a-M41
14	Route 14	912	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M39-M39a-M41
15	Route 15	1130	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
16	Route 16	896	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
17	Route 17	668	4P156g-4P156-IY15km-A380

SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY

International scientific-online conference

18	Route 18	550	M37-A380-M39-4P23n
19	Route 19	557	M37-A380-M39-M39a
20	Route 20	714	M37-A380-M39-M39a-M41
21	Route 21	634	M37-M37a-M39-A373-4P20
22	Route 22	852	M37-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
23	Route 23	618	M37-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
24	Route 24	1080	M37-A380
25	Route 25	184	4P23n-M41
26	Route 26	652	4P23n-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20
27	Route 27	870	4P23n-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
28	Route 28	636	4P23n-M39-M378-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
29	Route 29	1428	4P23n-M39-A380
30	Route 30	173	M39a-M41
31	Route 31	659	M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20
32	Route 32	877	M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
33	Route 33	643	M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
34	Route 34	1435	M39a-M39-A380
35	Route 35	816	M41-M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20
36	Route 36	1034	M41-M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-4P20-A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
37	Route 37	800	M41-M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-M34-M39-4P186
38	Route 38	1592	M41-M39a-M39-A380
39	Route 39	95	4P20-A373-4P26-M34-M39-4P186
40	Route 40	1512	4P20-A373-M39-M37a-M37-A380
41	Route 41	218	A376-4P44b-A373b-A373
42	Route 42	313	A373-A373b-4P44b-A376-4P20-A373-4P26-M34-M39-4P186
43	Route 43	1730	A373-A373b-4P44b-A376-4P20-A373-M39-M37a-M37-A380
44	Route 44	1496	4P186-M39-M34-A373-M39-M37a-M37-A380

SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY

International scientific-online conference

45	Route 45	1546	A381-A380-(4K-41-4R-174-4R-191-4R-176-4R-176v)-M37-M37a-M39-A373-A373b-4R126-A373
46	Route 46	1396	4R15g-4R156-IY-A380-M37-M37a-M39-A373-A373b-4R126-A373
47	Route 47	1025	M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - A373b-4R126 - A373
48	Route 48	1044	4R23n - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 -A373 - A373b - 4R126 -A373
49	Route 49	1058	M39a-M39-A378-M37a-M39-A373-A373b-4R126A373
50	Route 50	1208	M41-M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a -M39 - A373 - - A373b -4R126 - A373
51	Route 51	502	A373 - 4R126-A373b - A373 M34- M39-4R18
52	Route 52	1946	-A373-4R126-A373b-A373-A373-M39-M37a-M37-A380 (4K-41-4R174-4R191-4R176-4R176v
53	Route 53	890	A381 - A380 (4K41 - 4R174 - 4R191 - 4R176 - 4R176v - M37 - M37a - A377
54	Route 54	1120	A381 - A380 - M37 - M37a -M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
55	Route 55	1170	A381 - A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
56	Route 56	1088	A381 - A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
57	Route 57	690	4R156g - 4R156 -A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A377-IY
58	Route 58	1000	4R156g - 4R156 A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 -M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694 15-IY
59	Route 59	970	4R156g - 4R156 along the roads, along the way A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a-IY
60	Route 60	888	4R156g - 4R156 along the roads, along the way A380 - M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29-IY
61	Route 61	412	M37 - M37a - M39 - A377
62	Route 62	722	M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694

SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY

International scientific-online conference

63	Route 63	692	The border of Turkmenistan - Olot vehicle launch pad (Bukhara region) - Zangiota vehicle launch pad (Tashkent region) - the border of Kazakhstan.
64	Route 64	610	M37 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
65	Route 65	420	4R23n - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A377
66	Route 66	740	- 4R23n - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
67	Route 67	710	4R23n - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
68	Route 68	628	4R23n - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
69	Route 69	427	M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A377
70	Route 70	747	M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8
71	Route 71	717	M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
72	Route 72	635	M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
73	Route 73	590	M41 - M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - A377
74	Route 74	904	M41 - M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
75	Route 75	874	M41 - M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
76	Route 76	792	M41 - M39a - M39 - A378 - M37a - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
77	Route 77	298	A377 - M39 - A373 - 4R20
78	Route 78	516	A377 - M39 - A373 - 4R20
79	Route 79	676	A377 - M39 - A373 - A373b - 4R126 - A373
80	Route 80	383	A377 - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
81	Route 81	352	A377 - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4
82	Route 82	282	A377 - M39 - A373 - M34 - M39 - 4R186
83	Route 83	267	A377 - M39 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
84	Route 84	1290	A377 - M39 - M37a - M37 - A380 4K41 - 4R174 - 4R191 - 4R176 - 4R176v

85	Route 85	225	4R20 - A373- M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
86	Route 86	194	4R20 - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
87	Route 87	112	4R20 - A373 - M34 - 4R29
88	Route 88	468	A376 - 4K894 - 4K924 - 4R17e - A373b -A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
89	Route 89	437	A376 - 4K894 - 4K924 - 4r17e - A373b - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
90	Route 90	359	A376 - 4K894 - 4K924 - 4R17e - A373b - A373 - M34 - 4R29
91	Route 91	378,4	A373 - A373b - 4R44b - A376 4R20 - A373 - 4R26 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
92	Route 92	347	A373 - A373b - 4R44b - A376 - 4R20 - A373 - 4R26 - M34
93	Route 93	346,5	A373 - A373b - 4R44b - A376
94	Route 94	520	A373 - 4R126 - A373b - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - M39 - 4R8 - 4K694
95	Route 95	490	A373 - 4R126 - A373b - A373 - M34 - M39 - M39b - 4R4 - 4R4a
96	Route 96	506	A373 - 4R126 - A373b - A373
97	Route 97	1546	4K694 - 4R8 - M39 - M39b - M39 - M34 - A373 - M39 - M37a - M37 - A380 (4K41 - 4R174 - 4R191 - 4R176 - 4R176v
98	Route 98	1515	4R4a - 4R4 - M39b - M39 - M34 - A373 - M39 - M37a - M37 - A380 (4K41 - 4R174 - 4R191 - 4R176 - 4R176v
99	Route 99	1480	4R29 - M34 - A373 - M39 - M37a - M37 - A380 (4K41 - 4R174 - 4R191 - 4R176 - 4R176v

The purpose of creating these roads is to create facilities for international carriers transiting through our Republic [8].

References:

1. L.Y.Bakirov M.A.Nurdinov "Avtomobillarda xalqaro yuk tashish qoidalari". T. 2021 370 bet.
2. Курганов В.М., Миротин Л.Б., «Международные грузовые автомобильное перевозки» Учебное пособие для вузов. Тверь, 2000-131с.

3. Muqimova D., Nurdinov M. COMPLIANCE WITH RESPONSIBILITY AND WORK REGIMES OF DRIVERS IN LEGAL REGULATORY DOCUMENTS DUE TO ACCIDENTS IN THE TRANSPORTATION OF INTERNATIONAL GOODS BY TRUCKS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 15-25.
4. Shukurov M. M. et al. Roads, road lines and thermoplastic products used in their drawing //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 4. – C. 258-263.
5. Shukurov M. et al. Highways, Functions And Importance //The American Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 04. – C. 1-6.
6. Xushnud Rahmonov, Xayrullo Odilov ORGANIZATION OF QUALITY TRANSPORT SERVICE - Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research ISSN: 2278-4853 Vol. 11, Issue 5, May 2022 DOI: 10.5958/2278-4853.2022.00122.7
7. Muqimova D. et al. LOCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE MAIN NETWORKS OF WORLD TRANSPORT //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 279-284.
8. “Avtomobilda xorijiy yuk tashuvchilarning o‘zbekiston respublikasi hududiga kirishlari, bo‘lishlari, yuk olib o‘tishlari va undan chiqib ketishlari tartibi” to‘g‘risida Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2011 yil 9 dekabrda 323-son qarori.